

Supplementary Information

Potential for real-time health and welfare monitoring in experimental rabies infection in red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) using telemetric data collected with implants

Julie Teresa Shapiro^{1*}, Eric Morignat¹, Denise Dubois², Nicolas Penel³, Aurélien Madouasse⁴,
Emmanuelle Robardet³, Jean-Philippe Amat¹, Viviane Hénaux¹, Sandrine Lesellier³

¹University of Lyon - French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health and Safety (ANSES), Epidemiology and Surveillance Support Unit, 31 Ave Tony Garnier, 69007, Lyon, France

²World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH), Brussels Sub-Regional Representation, Boulevard du Jardin Botanique 55, 1000, Brussels, Belgium

³Nancy Laboratory for Rabies and Wildlife, Agence Nationale de Sécurité Sanitaire de l'Alimentation, de l'Environnement et du Travail (ANSES), 54220, Malzéville, France

⁴Oniris, INRAE, BIOEPAR, Nantes 44300, France

Figure n°1. Suture tabs

Figure S1. An easyTEL+ implant (model ET-M2-ETA - Emka Technologies, France) used in this study.

Table S1. Ranking of models (Shewhart and EWMA with varying confidence levels or σ , respectively) for anomaly detection for fox 0fae. Models are ordered by rank starting from the best, based on the lowest number of alarms during the calibration period (Calibration alarms), the greatest number of consecutive alarms before death, and the lowest number of single alarms in the monitoring period. Total alarms indicate total number of alarms during the monitoring period (considered as true positives).

Measure	Time period	Algorithm	CL / $n\sigma$	Calibration alarms	Consecutive alarms	Singleton alarms	Total alarms
Activity	Daily	EWMA	2	0	10	0	15
Activity	Day-time	EWMA	2	0	9	1	13
Activity	Daily	EWMA	3	0	7	1	8
Activity	Night-time	EWMA	2	0	6	0	6
Activity	Day-time	EWMA	3	0	6	1	7
Activity	Daily	EWMA	4	0	5	1	6
Activity	Night-time	EWMA	3	0	5	0	5
Activity	Night-time	EWMA	4	0	5	0	5
Activity	Daily	Shewhart	0.997	0	5	0	5
Activity	Daily	Shewhart	0.9999	0	5	0	5
Activity	Day-time	Shewhart	0.9999	0	4	0	4
Activity	Day-time	EWMA	4	0	4	1	5
Activity	Day-time	Shewhart	0.997	0	4	1	5
Activity	Night-time	Shewhart	0.9999	0	2	0	2
Activity	Night-time	Shewhart	0.997	0	2	1	3
Activity	Night-time	Shewhart	0.95	1	6	0	6
Activity	Day-time	Shewhart	0.95	1	4	3	9
Activity	Daily	Shewhart	0.95	2	7	3	10
Temperature	Night-time	EWMA	4	3	0	0	13
Temperature	Night-time	Shewhart	0.9999	2	0	2	9
Temperature	Daily	EWMA	4	4	4	0	14
Temperature	Daily	Shewhart	0.9999	4	4	2	11
Temperature	Night-time	EWMA	3	4	0	0	14
Temperature	Night-time	Shewhart	0.997	4	0	2	9
Temperature	Day-time	EWMA	4	5	4	0	13
Temperature	Day-time	EWMA	3	6	5	0	15

Temperature	Daily	Shewhart	0.997	6	4	2	13
Temperature	Day-time	Shewhart	0.9999	6	4	4	10
Temperature	Night-time	EWMA	2	6	0	0	15
Temperature	Night-time	Shewhart	0.95	7	0	3	13
Temperature	Day-time	Shewhart	0.95	8	7	2	14
Temperature	Day-time	Shewhart	0.997	8	6	2	13
Temperature	Day-time	EWMA	2	8	5	0	15
Temperature	Daily	EWMA	2	8	4	0	15
Temperature	Daily	EWMA	3	8	4	0	15
Temperature	Daily	Shewhart	0.95	8	4	1	14

Table S2. Ranking of models (Shewhart and EWMA with varying confidence levels or $n\sigma$, respectively) for anomaly detection for fox 0faf. Models are ordered by rank starting from the best, based on the lowest number of alarms during the calibration period (Calibration alarms), the greatest number of consecutive alarms before the end of data collection (8 days before death), and the lowest number of single alarms in the monitoring period. Total alarms indicate total number of alarms during the monitoring period (considered as true positives). Only models that produced at least one alarm are included.

Measure	Time period	Algorithm	CL / $n\sigma$	Calibration alarms	Consecutive alarms	Singleton alarms	Total alarms
Activity	Daily	EWMA	3	0	6	0	6
Activity	Daily	EWMA	4	0	2	2	4
Activity	Day-time	EWMA	2	0	2	0	5
Activity	Night-time	EWMA	4	0	2	0	2
Activity	Daily	EWMA	2	1	8	0	8
Temperature	Night-time	Shewhart	0.9999	1	0	2	2
Temperature	Day-time	Shewhart	0.9999	2	0	1	5
Activity	Night-time	EWMA	3	3	3	0	3
Temperature	Daily	Shewhart	0.997	3	0	1	5
Temperature	Daily	Shewhart	0.9999	3	0	1	5
Temperature	Day-time	Shewhart	0.997	3	0	1	5
Temperature	Night-time	Shewhart	0.997	3	0	2	2
Temperature	Day-time	Shewhart	0.95	4	0	1	6
Activity	Night-time	EWMA	2	5	4	0	6
Temperature	Daily	Shewhart	0.95	5	0	1	6
Temperature	Night-time	Shewhart	0.95	5	0	2	4

Table S3. Ranking of models (Shewhart and EWMA with varying confidence levels or $n\sigma$, respectively) for anomaly detection for fox 0fb1. Models are ordered by rank starting from the best, based on the lowest number of alarms during the calibration period (Calibration alarms), the greatest number of consecutive alarms before the end of data collection (12 days before death), and the lowest number of single alarms in the monitoring period. Total alarms indicate total number of alarms during the monitoring period (considered as true positives).

Measure	Time period	Algorithm	CL / $n\sigma$	Consecutive alarms	Calibration alarms	Singleton alarms	Total alarms
Activity	Night-time	EWMA	4	8	0	0	8
Activity	Day-time	EWMA	3	3	0	0	5
Temperature	Daily	EWMA	4	5	0	1	6
Temperature	Daily	Shewhart	0.9999	3	0	3	6
Temperature	Day-time	EWMA	3	3	0	1	6
Temperature	Day-time	EWMA	4	3	0	1	4
Activity	Daily	EWMA	3	0	0	1	7
Activity	Daily	EWMA	4	0	0	0	2
Activity	Daily	Shewhart	0.997	0	0	2	2
Activity	Daily	Shewhart	0.9999	0	0	1	1
Activity	Day-time	EWMA	4	0	0	2	2
Activity	Day-time	Shewhart	0.9999	0	0	2	2
Activity	Day-time	EWMA	2	6	1	0	6
Temperature	Daily	EWMA	3	5	1	0	7
Activity	Day-time	Shewhart	0.997	0	1	2	2
Activity	Night-time	Shewhart	0.9999	0	1	2	4
Temperature	Night-time	EWMA	4	3	2	0	3
Activity	Night-time	Shewhart	0.997	0	2	2	6
Temperature	Day-time	Shewhart	0.9999	0	2	4	4
Temperature	Night-time	Shewhart	0.997	0	2	4	4
Temperature	Night-time	Shewhart	0.9999	0	2	3	3
Activity	Night-time	EWMA	2	8	3	0	8
Activity	Night-time	EWMA	3	8	3	0	8
Temperature	Night-time	EWMA	3	6	3	0	6
Temperature	Daily	EWMA	2	5	3	0	7

Activity	Daily	EWMA	2	0	3	1	8
Activity	Daily	Shewhart	0.95	0	3	2	4
Activity	Day-time	Shewhart	0.95	0	3	1	3
Activity	Night-time	Shewhart	0.95	0	3	1	7
Temperature	Day-time	Shewhart	0.997	0	3	5	5
Temperature	Daily	Shewhart	0.95	3	4	3	6
Temperature	Daily	Shewhart	0.997	3	4	3	6
Temperature	Day-time	EWMA	2	3	4	1	6
Temperature	Day-time	Shewhart	0.95	3	5	3	6
Temperature	Night-time	EWMA	2	6	6	1	7
Temperature	Night-time	Shewhart	0.95	0	7	3	5

Table S4. Ranking of models (Shewhart and EWMA with varying confidence levels or $n\sigma$, respectively) for anomaly detection for fox 0fb0. Models are ordered by rank starting from the best, based on the lowest number of alarms during the calibration period (Calibration alarms) and the lowest number of singleton alarms in the monitoring period. This fox survived inoculation. Total alarms indicate total number of alarms during the monitoring period.

Measure	Time period	Algorithm	CL / $n\sigma$	Calibration alarms	Singleton alarms	Total alarms
Activity	Day-time	EWMA	4	0	0	21
Activity	Daily	EWMA	2	0	1	45
Activity	Daily	EWMA	3	0	1	34
Activity	Day-time	EWMA	3	0	1	25
Activity	Night-time	EWMA	2	0	1	39
Activity	Night-time	EWMA	3	0	1	31
Temperature	Daily	EWMA	4	0	1	49
Activity	Daily	EWMA	4	0	2	25
Activity	Daily	Shewhart	0.997	0	2	16
Activity	Day-time	EWMA	2	0	2	30
Activity	Day-time	Shewhart	0.9999	0	2	14
Activity	Night-time	EWMA	4	0	2	23
Activity	Night-time	Shewhart	0.9999	0	2	2
Activity	Daily	Shewhart	0.95	0	3	29
Activity	Night-time	Shewhart	0.997	0	3	9
Activity	Daily	Shewhart	0.9999	0	4	9
Activity	Day-time	Shewhart	0.997	0	5	21
Activity	Night-time	Shewhart	0.95	0	6	26
Activity	Day-time	Shewhart	0.95	1	2	27
Temperature	Daily	Shewhart	0.9999	1	6	30
Temperature	Daily	EWMA	3	2	2	54
Temperature	Day-time	EWMA	4	2	2	44
Temperature	Night-time	Shewhart	0.9999	2	4	21
Temperature	Daily	Shewhart	0.997	3	2	40
Temperature	Day-time	EWMA	3	3	2	49
Temperature	Day-time	Shewhart	0.9999	3	6	29

Temperature	Day-time	Shewhart	0.997	4	2	39
Temperature	Daily	EWMA	2	5	1	57
Temperature	Daily	Shewhart	0.95	6	2	49
Temperature	Day-time	Shewhart	0.95	6	2	49
Temperature	Night-time	EWMA	4	6	6	26
Temperature	Night-time	Shewhart	0.997	6	7	26
Temperature	Day-time	EWMA	2	7	1	53
Temperature	Night-time	EWMA	3	7	4	32
Temperature	Night-time	Shewhart	0.95	7	7	33
Temperature	Night-time	EWMA	2	8	4	40
